

Structural Creep Prediction of the Bridge Fully Built with Flax-fiber Reinforced Polymer Composites

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ABSTRACT

Flax fiber-reinforced polymer (FFRP) composites are environmentally friendly construction materials. However, their creep behavior poses a new concern for structural analysis in FFRP-based structures. This study develops a systematic approach to predict the creep of an FFRP bridge. The proper constitutive model for the description of FFRP creep is first developed based on the creep test, followed by numerical simulation. A numerical simulation model in Abaqus, incorporating anisotropic creep behavior in the UMAT subroutine, is utilized to investigate structural creep. The simulation results demonstrate the necessity of establishing a three-dimensional anisotropic model to analyze the creep behavior FFRP structures.

KEYWORDS

Flax fiber; Creep; Numerical simulation

INTRODUCTION

Fiber Reinforced Polymer (FRP) materials are composite materials composed of a polymer matrix and reinforcing fibers. These materials have gained significant popularity in practical engineering applications due to their numerous advantages, such as high strength, ease of manufacturing, fatigue resistance, and corrosion resistance. Moreover, the use of FRP can significantly reduce the overall weight of the structure. However, the predominant fibers currently utilized in FRP production are carbon fiber and glass fiber, which are non-renewable and require high energy consumption during their manufacturing process.

In light of growing environmental concerns and the increasing demand for sustainable construction materials, the development of natural fibers derived from plants has gained substantial momentum in recent years. Among these alternative materials, flax fiber has emerged as a promising substitute for traditional fibers within the construction industry. Flax fiber reinforced polymer (FFRP) has been successfully employed in various engineering projects, such as reinforcing concrete columns (Akin & Rashidi, 2021), strengthening concrete beams (Wroblewski et al., 2016), and serving as an outer panel in sandwich structures alongside core foam (Betts et al., 2021) (Sharaf & Fam, 2011) (Ferdous et al., 2018). Notably, in 2016, the world witnessed the completion of the first-ever pedestrian bridge constructed entirely from flax fiber reinforced polymer (FFRP) in Eindhoven, the Netherlands (Blok et al., 2019). This pioneering engineering endeavor exemplifies the immense potential of FFRP in load-bearing structural applications. Nevertheless, it is crucial to further investigate the mechanical properties of FFRP, particularly its viscoelastic behavior such as creep, to ensure its optimal performance in structural engineering.

The durability and reliability of composite structures are significantly influenced by the viscosity of the materials (Nedjar, 2014) (Berardi & Mancusi, 2012). The rheological properties of FRPs play a crucial role in determining the long-term performance of newly constructed composite components or

the reinforcement of existing structural elements. Consequently, the migration of stresses from FRP reinforcement to the base structural element, caused by the creep sensitivity of the materials, can lead to a degradation in the effectiveness of the reinforcement (Spelter et al., 2019) (Ascione et al., 2011). In the field of civil engineering, the creep effect is often addressed in national and international guidelines with conservative methodologies for the design and it's not able to provide the creep development of the structure with time. Due to the special nature of anisotropy creep, it is necessary to conduct structure creep analysis before structural design to ensure the structural safety of the engineering made of FFRP.

To anticipate potential creep during the early stages of project design, it is necessary to give due consideration and calculation to the viscoelastic characteristics of FFRP. This paper discusses anisotropic creep modeling of structures fabricated from FFRP, using the example of an already constructed bridge. Creep testing and material preparation work to obtain creep properties are first described. Then, based on the creep test results, the actual effects of different creep constitutive models applied to FFRP were introduced and compared. Then the 3D anisotropic model of the bridge is established based on the selected viscoelastic constitutive model on the Abaqus platform to carry out the structural creep analysis.

Material and testing methodology

Sample preparation

Vacuum infusion was utilized to produce FFRP plates, characterized by a 40% fiber volume fraction. The composite material consisted of unsaturated polyester serving as the matrix, while unidirectional flax fabrics with an areal density of 280 g/m^2 provided the reinforcement. Prior to the vacuum injection process, the flax fabrics were stored in a controlled climate chamber set at a temperature of 23°C and relative humidity of 65%. Throughout the injection process, the infusion system maintained a vacuum pressure of -1 Bar.

Following the resin injection, a 12-hour post-curing phase at 120°C was implemented subsequent to an initial curing process lasting 6 hours. Subsequently, all manufactured sample plates were placed in an environment with a temperature of 23°C and a relative humidity of 60% for a minimum of 2 weeks to ensure complete curing. Subsequently, the plates were meticulously cut into rectangular specimens measuring $40 \times 5 \text{ mm}^2$ for the accelerated creep test and $250 \times 15 \text{ mm}^2$ for the long-term tensile creep test.

Figure 1: Creep Test Equipment

Creep test

For the investigation of the long-term tensile creep behavior of FFRP samples, custom-made creep test equipment was developed, as depicted in Figure 1. To ensure that the applied force on the sample aligns with the fiber direction, the sample was meticulously positioned perpendicular to the clamps, and the weights were aligned with the sample. The fiber volume fraction of the sample used in the long-term test remained consistent with that employed in the accelerated creep test. Strain gauges were installed on each side of the sample to measure the creep-induced strain changes. To achieve a creep stress of 10 MPa, the corresponding weight was calculated based on the sample size. The entire testing system was placed within a climate room, maintaining a constant relative humidity of 60% at a temperature of 20°C. The long-term loading process lasted for 2000 hours, allowing for an extensive assessment of creep behavior.

Theoretical viscoelastic model of creep behavior

The experimental results revealed a nearly linear viscoelastic response of the examined FFRP specimens, consistent with findings reported in previous studies. These findings suggest a delayed response when subjected to creep stresses below 40% of their corresponding strength. Within the linear viscoelasticity stage, the Kelvin-Voigt model and Burgers model (Burgers, 1939) as shown in Figure 2 are popular and have been widely used to describe the creep behavior of the FRP material. However, the creep of flax fiber composites is more complex than that of traditional composites like GFRP, it is necessary to compare and choose a theoretical constitutive model suitable for FFRP in order to accurately describe the creep properties exhibited by the materials in the experiment.

Figure 2: Schematic diagram of the creep constitutive model

Kelvin-Voigt model

The Kelvin-Voigt model is a classic viscoelastic model composed of a linear spring and a damper connected in parallel (Bland, 1960) as shown in Figure 2(a). It is used to describe the strain response of a material after being subjected to external stress. The Kelvin model consists of a spring and a damper in series, where the spring represents the elastic behavior of the material, and the damper represents the viscous behavior of the material. The Kelvin model can be expressed by the following differential equation:

$$\sigma(t) = E \cdot \varepsilon(t) + \eta \cdot \frac{d\varepsilon(t)}{dt} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where the $\sigma(t)$ is the stress, $\varepsilon(t)$ is the strain, E is the elastic modulus of the spring, and η is the viscous damping coefficient of the damper. However, in practical applications, this model is rarely used in the viscoelastic calculation of composite materials because it cannot reflect the instantaneous elastic deformation. In order to overcome this shortcoming, it was found in previous studies that the generalized Kelvin-Voigt model (Figure 2(b)) formed by the combination of multiple Kelvin models can better reflect the creep behavior of composite materials, the constitutive equation of the generalized Kelvin-Voigt model is as follows:

$$\sigma(t) = \sum_{i=1}^n E_i \cdot \varepsilon(t) + \eta_i \cdot \frac{d\varepsilon(t)}{dt} \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where the $\sigma(t)$ is the stress, $\varepsilon(t)$ is the strain, E_i is the elastic modulus of the i_{th} spring, η_i is the viscous damping coefficient of the i_{th} damper, and n is the total Kelvin-Voigt elements in the model. In order to consider the creep behavior of the material, the generalized Kelvin-Voigt model can be transferred in the form of

$$J(t) = J_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n J_i \left[1 - \exp\left(-\frac{t}{\tau_i}\right) \right] \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where $J(t)$ is the creep compliance at time t , J_0 is the instantaneous compliance, and J_i and τ_i are the characteristics constants derived from the Kelvin-Voigt elements of the model. Based on the form of the model, it can be found that the number of spring-damper units will affect the fineness of the model to reflect creep. The generalized Kelvin model with four elements and six elements was applied to describe the creep test results as shown in Figure 3. The results indicated that both of them can provide a proper description of creep behavior in the initial stage, but four-element Kelvin overestimates the creep with time. On the other hand, the six-element Kelvin can fit the creep test results well.

Burgers model

The Burgers model is another classical linear viscoelastic model used to describe the time-dependent behavior of materials under sustained stress. It was proposed by H. G. Burgers in the 1930s and has been widely used in many fields of material engineering and mechanics research. The Burgers model is based on two key assumptions: elastic deformation and viscous deformation. By connecting a Maxwell unit and a Kelvin unit in series, the Burgers model divides the creep strain of an FFRP into three parts: the instantaneous elastic deformation described by the spring in the Maxwell unit to reflect the instantaneous spring back of a material when a force is applied; viscoelastic deformation (Kelvin unit) describes the viscoelastic deformation; and the viscous deformation describes by the Maxwell dash-pot over a long period of time. The constitutive equation of the Burgers viscoelastic model can be described as

$$\frac{E_2}{\eta_2} \sigma + \left(1 + \frac{E_2}{E_1} + \frac{\eta_1}{\eta_2} \right) \dot{\sigma} + \frac{\eta_1}{E_1} \ddot{\sigma} = E_2 \dot{\varepsilon} + \eta_1 \ddot{\varepsilon} \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

where ε is the creep strain, σ is the stress, E_1 and E_2 are the elastic modulus of the Maxwell and the Kelvin springs, and η_1 and η_2 are viscosities of the Maxwell and the Kelvin dashpots. By Laplace the Laplace transform the

$$\varepsilon(t) = \frac{\sigma}{E_1} + \frac{\sigma}{E_2} \left[1 - \exp\left(-t \frac{E_2}{\eta_2}\right) \right] + \frac{\sigma}{\eta_1} t \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

where $\varepsilon(t)$ is the creep strain at time t , σ is the stress, and t is time. The creep compliance $J(t)$ can be described as

$$J(t) = \frac{1}{E_1} + \frac{1}{E_2} \left[1 - \exp\left(-t \frac{E_2}{\eta_2}\right) \right] + \frac{1}{\eta_1} t \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

The strength of the Burgers model lies in its simplicity and solvability. It provides a reasonable approximation to the fundamental viscoelastic behavior of materials and enables an accurate

description of the response of many materials on short- and medium-term timescales. However, the Burgers model cannot capture some complex nonlinear and long-term creep behaviors well, and more complex models or improvements to the Burgers model may be needed for these situations. By applying the Burgers model to fit the sample creep test results of FFRP (Figure 3), it's found that the fitting results are efficient which means using the Burgers model to describe the creep behavior of FFRP samples is a good choice. However, the complex form of the Burgers model makes it hard to be transferred into an anisotropic form to consider the three-dimension mode analysis.

Findley power law

Findley proposed an alternative method to model the long-term creep behavior of polymers and FRP materials subjected to constant stress (Findley & Davis., 1976). This empirical equation, which encompasses both elastic and nonelastic viscoelasticity, offers a viable solution. Findley defines the total axial strain as a combination of separable time-independent and time-dependent deformation components. This approach provides a comprehensive framework to accurately describe the creep characteristics of these materials over extended periods of time. By adopting this methodology, a more comprehensive understanding of the viscoelastic behavior of polymers and FRP materials can be achieved, facilitating improved predictions and analysis of their long-term structural performance.

$$\varepsilon(t) = \varepsilon_0 + \varepsilon_{cr}(t) = \varepsilon_0 + m \left(\frac{t}{t_{dim}} \right)^n \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

where $\varepsilon(t)$ is the strain at time t , ε_0 is the initial elastic strain, m is the constants dependent on the temperature and stress level, n is the stress-independent material coefficient, and t_{dim} is a reference time. Under the linear viscoelastic hypothesis, Findley's law can be simplified in terms of creep compliance as

$$J(t) = J_0 + m_1 \cdot \left(\frac{t}{t_{dim}} \right)^n \quad \text{Eq. 8}$$

where m_1 is material coefficients. In general, the Findley power can describe creep under simple loads well, but it is not particularly good at complex loads and long-term prediction due to the simple parameters. The fitting results to creep test results indicates that Findley power law is more of a straight line (Figure 3), this is due to the sample form of the model. The Findley power law is an empirical model to describe the creep behavior, which can't provide physical meaning. The suitable application scenarios of the Findley method are to describe existing long-term creep results but not in the analysis.

Figure 3: Creep test results and constitutive model fitting curve

Numerical simulation

In order to simulate and predict the structural creep behavior of FFRP bridges, a numerical simulation model was established using the Abaqus numerical simulation platform. This chapter will introduce three aspects: the definition of the constitutive model of the material, the introduction and modeling method of the numerical model of the bridge, and the numerical simulation results of the creep of the bridge.

Three-dimension Orthotropic Creep Constitutive Model

Based on the selection and comparison results of the constitutive models used to describe the creep above, the generalized Kelvin model with six elements is selected to describe the creep behavior of the materials used in the research object (FFRP bridge). Since the analysis of structural creep needs to consider the anisotropic mechanical behavior under three-dimensional conditions, it is necessary to extend the creep behavior under uniaxial loads to three-dimensional anisotropic materials for analysis when simulating structural creep.

Since the actual bridge is constructed by laying single-fiber composite materials through ordinary angles, the materials used can be considered transversely isotropic materials. Therefore, the constitutive structure of a three-dimensional orthotropic material considering creep strain is

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{D}(\boldsymbol{\varepsilon} - \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{\text{creep}}) \quad \text{Eq. 9}$$

where $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the stress matrix, \mathbf{D} is the elastic stiffness matrix, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is the strain array, and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{\text{creep}}$ is the creep strain array.

The linear Boltzmann Equation (Eq. 10) is introduced to represent the linear viscoelastic behavior under actual loading conditions.

$$\varepsilon(t) = D(t)\sigma_0 + \int_0^t D(t-\tau) \frac{d\sigma(\tau)}{d\tau} d\tau \quad \text{Eq. 10}$$

where $D(\cdot)$ is the compliance, and t is the time.

Fully considering the time-dependent viscoelastic properties of FFRP under three-dimensional conditions, the creep strain matrix of the material can be expressed as:

$$[\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}]^{\text{creep}} = \begin{bmatrix} \int_0^t \Delta D_{11}(t-\tau) \frac{\partial(\sigma_1^r)}{\partial \tau} d\tau - \nu_{12} \int_0^t \Delta D_{11}(t-\tau) \frac{\partial(\sigma_2^r)}{\partial \tau} d\tau - \nu_{13} \int_0^t \Delta D_{11}(t-\tau) \frac{\partial(\sigma_3^r)}{\partial \tau} d\tau \\ -\nu_{12} \int_0^t \Delta D_{11}(t-\tau) \frac{\partial(\sigma_1^r)}{\partial \tau} d\tau + \int_0^t \Delta D_{22}(t-\tau) \frac{\partial(\sigma_2^r)}{\partial \tau} d\tau - \nu_{23} \int_0^t \Delta D_{11}(t-\tau) \frac{\partial(\sigma_3^r)}{\partial \tau} d\tau \\ \int_0^t \Delta D_{11}(t-\tau) \frac{\partial(\sigma_1^r)}{\partial \tau} d\tau + \int_0^t \Delta D_{11}(t-\tau) \frac{\partial(\sigma_2^r)}{\partial \tau} d\tau + \int_0^t \Delta D_{11}(t-\tau) \frac{\partial(\sigma_3^r)}{\partial \tau} d\tau \\ 2(1+\nu_{23}) \int_0^t \Delta D_{66}(t-\tau) \frac{\partial(\tau_{23}^r)}{\partial \tau} d\tau \\ \int_0^t \Delta D_{66}(t-\tau) \frac{\partial(\tau_{31}^r)}{\partial \tau} d\tau \\ \int_0^t \Delta D_{66}(t-\tau) \frac{\partial(\tau_{12}^r)}{\partial \tau} d\tau \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{Eq. 11}$$

The elastic stiffness matrix in Eq. 9 can be expressed as

$$[D] = [S]^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & & & & & & \\ -\nu_{12}S_{11} & S_{22} & Sym & & & & \\ -\nu_{12}S_{11} & -\nu_{23}S_{11} & S_{22} & & & & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 2(1+\nu_{23})S_{22} & & & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & S_{66} & & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & S_{66} & \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \quad \text{Eq. 12}$$

The creep compliance parameters in the longitudinal, transverse, and in-plane shear directions can be obtained by curve-fitting the creep test results. The parameters in Eq. 11 are listed in Table 1.

Table 1: Parameters of the six-element Kelvin-Voigt viscoelastic model

n	$D_{n,11}$ (GPa-1)	$\lambda_{n,11}$ (s ⁻¹)	$D_{n,22}$ (GPa-1)	$\lambda_{n,22}$ (s ⁻¹)	$D_{n,66}$ (GPa-1)	$\lambda_{n,66}$ (s ⁻¹)
1	0.531	2.19E-09	11.806	3.54E-11	0.236	1.71E-06
2	0.196	3.63E-07	1.084	1.62E-07	0.409	5.75E-09
3	0.338	2.45E-08	0.508	3.74E-06	0.130	5.40E-05
4	0.093	1.207	0.349	3.027	0.149	0.629
5	1.69E-10	0.090	1.16E-09	1.792	3.52E-10	0.326
6	1.01E-05	1.00E-07	1.30E-08	1.00E-07	8.83E-08	1.00E-07

Validation of the simulation method

To validate the accuracy of the simulation method based on the generalized Kelvin-Voigt viscoelastic model, a tensile creep was conducted on test on the FRFP samples using a universal testing machine, as shown in Figure 4(a). The creep test involved applying a constant stress of 15 MPa to the samples for a duration of 20 hours. The dimensions of the samples were 250 mm × 15 mm × 2 mm. The simulation work utilized the parameters listed in Table 1.

During the creep test, the creep strain was determined by measuring the change in length of the middle 50 mm of the sample using an optical measurement device. The simulation results were then compared with the experimental results, as illustrated in Figure 4(b). It was observed that the simulation model accurately predicted the secondary stage creep; however, it exhibited limited accuracy in predicting the primary stage creep. It is worth noting that the engineering analysis typically overlooks the primary stage creep due to its short duration and minimal influence on the overall creep development. Therefore, considering the limited significance of the primary stage creep, the simulation model's ability to replicate the overall creep behavior can be deemed acceptable.

a) creep test configuration

b) comparison of the simulation and measurement

Figure 4: The validation of the simulation

Numerical simulation of the structure

Numerical simulations were carried out in the ABAQUS environment. The aim was to simulate the creep behavior of the bridge over 1000 days to compare strains and displacements at different locations. The bridge prototype sits at Almere, Netherlands, which is a 15m long by 3m wide pedestrian bridge constructed of natural fiber composites (Figure 5). The bridge consists of ten foam cores and box girders made of multilayer laminates made of flax fiber-reinforced polyester. Choosing the appropriate method depends on the geometry of the structure as well as the required precision of results. Therefore, a 3D shell element (C3D8R) is used to represent the laminate. The FEM model consists of a multilayer laminate meshed with stacked continuous shell elements in the thickness direction. The mesh was refined using element division in the model, resulting in 79,064 nodes and 46,350 elements. Using the mat subroutine in Abaqus to define the three-dimensional viscoelastic constitutive relations of composite materials considering creep. The uniform pressure load converted from the self-weight was applied on the surface of the bridge and the instantaneous load during the service was ignored during the analysis.

Figure 5: Schematic diagram of bridge numerical simulation model

Numerical simulation results

After undergoing creep, there was a significant increase in the vertical displacement of all points on the bridge (Figure 5). This observation indicated the impact of creep deformation on the overall structural behavior of the bridge. The increase in vertical displacement can be attributed to the time-dependent viscoelastic properties of the bridge materials, which undergo gradual deformation under sustained loading. Upon further analysis of the cloud map, which represents the distribution of vertical displacement across the bridge, it was observed that the overall pattern and distribution of vertical displacement remained largely unchanged before and after creep. This consistency in the displacement distribution suggests that the bridge's vertical displacement variations can be assumed to follow a linear and uniform creep behavior.

The linear and uniform creep behavior implies that the vertical displacement at any given point on the bridge experiences a constant rate of change over time. This finding is significant as it allows for simplified modelling and prediction of the long-term deformation of the bridge under sustained loading conditions.

The consistent distribution of vertical displacement across the bridge can be attributed to various factors. Firstly, the uniformity in the creep behavior may be influenced by the homogeneity of the bridge materials and their consistent mechanical properties throughout the structure. This uniformity ensures that the materials exhibit similar time-dependent deformation characteristics, resulting in a consistent distribution of vertical displacement. Additionally, the design and construction of the bridge, including its geometry, support, and load distribution mechanisms can also contribute to the uniform creep behavior. A well-designed and properly constructed bridge with adequate support systems and load-bearing elements can help distribute the applied load more uniformly, minimizing localized stress concentrations and potential variations in creep behavior.

a) Elastic vertical displacement distribution b) Creep vertical displacement distribution
 Figure 6: The vertical displacement distribution at a) elastic stage and b) 1000-day creep

Furthermore, the environmental conditions to which the bridge is exposed can also play a role in uniform creep behavior. Factors such as temperature, humidity, and exposure to moisture can influence the creep properties of the bridge materials. If these factors are relatively consistent throughout the bridge, it can contribute to the uniformity of the creep behavior and displacement distribution. It is important to note that while the vertical displacement distribution remained largely unchanged, the overall magnitude of displacement increased significantly after the creep process. This emphasizes the importance of considering creep effects when evaluating the long-term performance and structural integrity of the bridge. The accumulated deformation due to creep over time can have implications for the safety, functionality, and serviceability of the bridge.

The observed significant increase in vertical displacement after creep indicates the impact of time-dependent deformation on the structural behavior of the bridge. However, the consistent distribution of vertical displacement across the bridge suggests a linear and uniform creep behavior. Understanding this behavior is crucial for accurately predicting and managing the long-term deformation of the bridge under sustained loading conditions. By considering the uniform creep behavior, engineers and designers can develop appropriate strategies to ensure the safety and durability of the bridge throughout its service life.

Conclusions

This study provides a systematic analysis method for the anisotropic viscoelasticity behavior of FRP composites to address the absence of viscoelastic simulation capabilities for anisotropic materials in commercial simulation software. Both experimental results and numerical simulations demonstrate the necessity of analyzing structural creep based on anisotropy conditions. These findings may help with practical implications for future design work of the FRP structure, enabling a better understanding of the impact of creep on structural deformation. However, the instantaneous load that happens on the bridge is unpredictable and the measurement data needs more study, further work is needed to obtain a comparison between creep development history and the simulation results.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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